

Workshop Report

Innovations in the research process in the Amazon

This document brings together the debates and reflections of the workshop participants "Innovations in the research process in the Amazon"

This is the Report of Workshop 4 of the project "Power of Connections: Harvesting Lessons and Strengthening Coalitions for Amazonian Conservation"

May 2026

Organizers		Collaborators
UNIVERSITY of FLORIDA		
GORDON AND BETTY MOORE FOUNDATION		

Report of the Workshop "**Innovations in the research process in the Amazon,**" held from December 8 to 11, 2025 in Puerto Maldonado, Madre de Dios, Peru.

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1. Pan-Amazonia
2. Innovation
3. Innovative practices
4. Impact
5. Inclusion
6. Research process

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

ACCA	Association for the Conservation of the Amazon Basin
CARE	Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, Ethics
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
eDNA	Environmental DNA
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
I's	Innovation, impact and inclusion
NGO	Non-governmental organization
NODO	NODO Conservation, Center of Tropical Ecology and Conservation
POC	Power of Connections
TCD	Tropical Conservation and Development program
UF	University of Florida
UFOPA	Federal University of Oeste do Pará
USA	Unites States of America
WCS	Wildlife Conservation Society

PRESENTATION

Between December 8 and 11, 2025, in Puerto Maldonado, Peru, researchers from universities, research centers, non-governmental organizations, among others, attended the workshop entitled "Innovations in the research process in the Amazon". This document is a record of ideas, experiences, and reflections on what it means to do conservation research in the Amazon in an innovative, inclusive, and impactful way.

The workshop was held within the framework of the project *The Power of Connections: Harvesting Lessons and Strengthening Coalitions for Amazonian Conservation* (hereafter POC), an initiative of the Tropical Conservation and Development Program at the University of Florida, in partnership with the Association for the Conservation of the Amazon Basin (ACCA), the Gabriel René Moreno Autonomous University, and the Universidade Federal do Oeste do Pará (UFOPA), and with financial support of the Gordon and Betty Moore Foundation.

The project is based on the premise that the Amazon, one of the most biodiverse and relevant ecosystems on the planet, is deeply connected to global social, political, and economic systems. Changes in international policies, investment decisions, or consumption patterns in other parts of the world directly affect Amazonian peoples and territories. Therefore, the central proposal of the project is to promote collective learning processes and strengthen coalitions and collaboration networks between Pan-Amazonian countries, connecting academic, ancestral, and local knowledge.

The project recognizes that effective conservation of the Amazon can only be achieved with Amazonians and not in spite of them. Thus, the knowledge, practices, and ways of life developed by Indigenous Peoples, traditional communities and local organizations offer valued innovative and replicable solutions to sustainability challenges.

The project started in January 2025 and ends in September 2026 and includes an international conference in Gainesville (USA) in February 2026 with the participation of thematic leaders and representatives of the partners involved. During this period, five thematic workshops will be held in different countries of the Amazon:

1. Sociobioeconomies and Conservation Finance (Brazil, May 2025)
2. Reshaping institutions for next generation conservation leaders in the Amazon (Bolivia, July 2025)
3. Collaborative management centered on indigenous peoples and local communities (Brazil, September 2025)
4. Innovations in the research process (Peru, December 2025)
5. Indigenous Rights and Governance Instruments (Ecuador, January 2025)

For this fourth workshop, thematic presentations, group discussions, and participatory exercises invited participants to reflect on how innovations in their research practices and conservation efforts have shaped each other. For 3.5 days, participants shared their methodological approaches, technological tools and knowledge co-creation practices. In empathetic and constructive ways, they questioned how these initiatives strengthen collaboration between local

communities, scientists and decision-makers, and generate social, political, and environmental impacts at different scales. The workshop also included spaces for systematization of learning, analysis of specific cases, and planning of next steps.

This report presents the key moments, the most relevant activities, and the topics addressed during the workshop as documented by the University of Florida team. The intention is that these contributions serve to promote and strengthen innovation in conservation research in the Amazon, contemplating its impact, inclusion, and the highest ethical standards.

Figure 1. Workshop participants

WORKSHOP ORGANIZATION PROCESS

This workshop, like the other four thematic workshops of the POC project, was the result of collaboration between the thematic leaders and the University of Florida (UF) team. The thematic leaders were selected several months in advance for their extensive experience in the Amazon and in the specific theme of the workshop. From then on, through weekly meetings, they and the UF team shaped the event: first by jointly defining the objectives and then by drawing up the list of participants, selected for the relevance of their knowledge and their approach to action.

A few months before the workshop, the facilitation team was also formed, led by two people: the facilitator of the UF team and an external facilitator from an Amazonian country, the latter also identified by the workshop organizing team. With the objectives defined and the participants confirmed, this team designed the agenda, which was subsequently reviewed and validated by the entire organizing group.

During the workshop, facilitation was carried out with a flexible and participatory approach, ensuring that each participant could contribute meaningfully to the discussions. Each day, and even sometimes during the sessions, the organizing team met briefly to reflect, evaluate the development of the process and, if necessary, adjust the agenda along the way.

Finally, after the workshop, the organizing team worked on the results, which were shared with the participants for validation in a virtual meeting. This was an iterative process, which was refined and strengthened with each workshop.

Objectives and agenda of the workshop

This workshop aimed to generate a space for dialogue, reflection, and cross-border and interdisciplinary exchange between researchers, members of non-governmental organizations, Indigenous representatives, and consultants – all centered on innovative research practices in support of Amazon conservation.

Specific objectives:

- To create community among professionals conducting research on biocultural and biodiversity conservation in the Amazon basin
- To advance thinking about innovation in research processes in the Amazon
- To promote an exchange of experiences in terms of methods, lessons learned, and successful experiences that can be replicated in other territories and locations
- Reflect on the ethical dimensions of innovation in research processes
- Collectively discuss and plan the next steps to strengthen biocultural conservation in the Amazon and the collaborative networks that support these efforts.

Table 1. Workshop agenda

Day	Central Theme	Activities
Day 1 12/08/2025	Building community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Welcome (UF and ACCA interventions) and presentation of POC team. - Presentation of the objectives, contents and methodology of the workshop. - Introduction of participants (who I am, where I work) and presentation of their key or important “object” from home. - Closing and logistical information for the following days.
Day 2 12/09/2025	Setting the stage: knowledge generation for biocultural conservation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Understanding Context and Establishing Common Foundations: Participants were asked to answer the following question: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. In the context of Amazon conservation research, what does innovation mean to you? 2. In your experience, what makes research in the Amazon impactful? 3. In your experience, what makes research in the Amazon inclusive? These questions were worked individually, in small groups and in plenary.

<p>Day 3 12/10/2025</p>	<p>Best practices in Action: Methods, Tools, and Ethical considerations</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sharing Experiences and Innovative Approaches: For a Poster fair, participants elaborated individual posters about their own research. The posters were placed in the walls and participants were divided into 2 groups to visit each poster and have time for Q&A. - Discussion on ethical considerations: in small groups, participants were invited to reflect on ethical dilemmas they have had to face in their research process, and how they navigated these dilemmas.
<p>Day 4 12/11/2025</p>	<p>Pulling it all together, Alliances, and the Road Ahead</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Defining Lessons Learned, Potential Products, and Collective Next Steps: participants were asked to answer the following questions on paper: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What idea or practice do I take away from the workshop? 2. What idea or practice did I bring to the workshop? <p>The answers were shared in plenary.</p> - Then, a space was opened for participants to decide in plenary about next actions or initiatives they would like to take as a group. The guiding question was: What would you like to do with this group? - Evaluation of the workshop and farewell

Workshop participants and their origins

The workshop counted with 24 participants plus the organizing team. Participant selection was carefully curated to have a diverse representation of innovative disciplinary and geographic experiences and researchers working toward biocultural conservation in the Amazon. As observed in Figure 2, meeting attendees came from non-governmental organizations (NGOs), universities, research institutes, biological stations, independent collectives, and consulting firms. Three also were representatives of Indigenous groups from Brazil and Guyana.

In addition to institutional diversity, the locations where participants developed their research covered a wide geographical range in the Amazon region, representing 6 countries (Figure 3). This diversity made it possible to identify regional patterns, but also to highlight the advances and challenges associated with conservation policies and actions in the different localities.

Figure 2. Distribution of participants by type of institutional affiliation

Figure 3. Distribution of participants according to the country where they carry out their research

Below is a complete list of workshop attendees, their email addresses, countries where they work, and institutional affiliation.

Table 2. Full list of workshop participants

Name	Organization	Email	Country of operations
Ana Maria Garrido	University of Florida	a.garrido@ufl.edu	Colombia
Ana Cristina Miranda Beas	Pontifical Catholic University of Peru	c.mirandab@pucp.pe	Peru
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Andrea Encalada Romero	Global Research and Solutions Center, Universidad San Francisco de Quito	aencalada@usfq.edu.ec	Ecuador
Angie Valdera Sandoval	ACCA	avaldera@conservacionamazonica.org	Peru
Bette Loiselle	University of Florida	bloiselle@latam.ufl.edu	USA

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Vanessa Luna	University of Florida	lunacelino.dv@ufl.edu	Peru/USA
Vania Tejeda Gomez	Smithsonian Institution and NODO conservation	vania@nodoconservation.org	Peru

DAY 1: GETTING TO KNOW EACH OTHER

1. Welcome to the workshop

The opening of the workshop took place during the night of December 8 at the Cabaña Quinta Hotel, in Puerto Maldonado. The welcoming remarks were given by Corine Vriesendorp, ACCA's Director of Science. In addition to thanking the participants, co-organizers and funders, Corine made a call to become aware of the place where we are: Puerto Maldonado. "This place, characterized by its high biodiversity, has also undergone recent and accelerated changes due to illegal gold mining. Therefore, being aware of the place where the workshop is held helps us to think not only about the richness of this region, but also about the challenges and complex dynamics that converge here."

Afterwards, UF Professor Karen Kainer introduced the organizing team starting with the other project co-leaders: Jonathan Dain, Pilar Useche, and Bette Loiselle; the postdoctoral researchers: Vanesa Luna and Johanna Espín; the co-facilitator: Pamela Montero; the doctoral student: Ana María Garrido; and the thematic leaders: Marisol Toledo and Myrian Sá Leitão Barboza. The latter made a brief contextualized the contents to be discussed during the following days.

The initial discussion of the thematic leaders proposed innovation as a broad process of knowledge production that is not just limited to the implementation of modern technologies, but also includes and recognizes ancestral knowledge. It was highlighted that the Amazon is the historical result of a continuous dialogue between different knowledge systems, where traditional landscape management practices are, in themselves, technological expressions. From this perspective, tools such as drones or GPS only make sense when they are articulated with local ways of knowing and caring for the territory. It was also stressed that research and innovations in research are fundamental elements for conservation, as they allow us to know, reconnect, and strengthen collaborative networks between people and communities.

2. Presentation of the participants

Subsequently, a round of presentation was held for all those attending the workshop. This exercise was developed as a collective dynamic aimed at situating people, their trajectories, and their links with the Amazon from the material and territorial perspectives. Each participant shared their name and institution, presented a significant object (which they had been asked to bring in advance from their homes) and located their name on a map in the place in the Amazon that they considered best represented them, thus building a collective cartography (Figure 5).

The shared objects accounted for a wide diversity of practices and ways of relating to research and conservation: field tools (diametric tapes, flashlights, binoculars), notebooks as objects for reflection and mediation with communities, dissemination materials and publications, seeds, handicrafts, food, and everyday objects from work in the territory. Beyond their practical function, these objects served as the first evidence of the participants' emotions, ethical commitments, long work trajectories, and open questions about how they seek, produce, share, and disseminate knowledge.

Figure 4. Presentation of significant objects of the participants

On the other hand, the exercise with the map revealed multiple “Amazons”, crossed by rivers, borders, Indigenous territories, protected areas and transformed landscapes. Thus, the diversity of points marked evidence of both the geographical breadth of the group and the depth and diversity of the relationships built with different Amazonian territories.

Figure 5. Collectively constructed map that highlights areas of research or places significant to participants

At the end of the dynamic, the facilitators reflected on the fact that both the map and the objects are an expression of the "power of connections" between people, places, knowledge, emotions, and practices. This initial moment allowed the diversity of the group to be recognized and laid the foundations of the workshop, posing the shared challenge of generating innovative ideas, strengthening new connections, and bringing concrete and applicable learning to the origin contexts of each participant.

3. Presentation of the POC project

To end the day, Karen Kainer placed the development of this workshop within the framework of the project *The Power of Connections*. This project comprises a series of five workshops held in different Amazonian countries; this is the fourth meeting. This workshop has been conceived as a space to reflect on how conservation research is being carried out in different contexts of the region and on the ways in which these processes have evolved over time.

Figure 6. Presentation of the project *The Power of Connections*, by Professor Karen Kainer

It was emphasized that the project is based on the recognition of diversity as a central strength: of territories, disciplines, trajectories, and knowledge systems. The articulation between biological and social perspectives was presented as a transversal element of the project. Likewise, the importance of nurturing the encounter with the experiences harvested from previous training and research processes of the participants was highlighted. Finally, it was emphasized that the participation of each person in the workshop was carefully thought out, taking into account specific trajectories and experiences considered strategic to enrich the dialogue.

1.2. Emerging expectations in the face-to-face workshop

Expressed expectations were expanded on the second day through a conversation exercise in pairs, designed to facilitate mutual knowledge and deepen individual and collective interests. In these conversations, there was a strong interest in learning about experiences developed in other Amazonian territories, as well as learning from people with diverse backgrounds, including non-academic knowledge and Indigenous experiences.

There was a particular expectation to explore the use of technologies applied to the monitoring of fauna and ecosystems, as well as to reflect on their articulation with traditional knowledge. At the same time, shared structural concerns emerged, such as access to financing to sustain conservation processes, the real impact of such mechanisms such as payments for environmental services, and the challenges faced by local economies in the face of illegal extractive activities.

Other expectations pointed to the need to strengthen the local bioeconomy, promote interculturality as an exchange of knowledge and experiences, and advance in the transformation of data and research into useful inputs for decision-making and advocacy for public policies. In this regard, the importance of thinking innovatively about advocacy strategies was underlined, as well as expanding frameworks of thought by incorporating indigenous perspectives and other forms of knowledge.

Thus, the workshop was understood as a space that should not only generate reflection, but also summon collective commitment and courage to address the complex challenges that Amazon conservation is going through.

Figure 8. Dynamics to share the expectations of the participants about the workshop

2. Exploring the Three I's: Innovation, Impact, and Inclusion

To guide the day's work, three key questions were presented that structured most of the day's discussions:

- a) *In the context of research on the conservation of the Amazon, what does innovation mean to you?*
- b) *In your experience, what makes research in the Amazon have an impact?*
- c) *In your experience, what makes research in the Amazon inclusive?*

Each question was addressed in two moments: first, through an individual reflection that allowed each participant to start from their own trajectory, practices, and learning; and then, in small groups, formed randomly, where these reflections were shared, contrasted, and enriched. At the end of each of the three question blocks, the groups presented the main points of the discussion in plenary, which facilitated the construction of a collective view.

2.1. Innovation in research for the conservation of the Amazon

The following are the main contributions of each group, presented in plenary, to the first guiding question: *What does innovation in research mean for the conservation of the Amazon?*

The first group to present mentioned that the diversity of perspectives of the people who participated in the discussion showed that innovation is not a neutral or homogeneous concept, but that it is crossed by the biases and trajectories of those who research. Based on this diversity of experiences, they defined innovation as a path to action that seeks to generate changes in an adaptive and comprehensive way, recognizing the specific problems that affect conservation in the Amazon. It was stressed that innovation implies leaving the "cabinet" and the "shelves", to take research to the field and adjust it to specific territorial contexts.

For the next group, the discussion started from the idea that innovation is no longer an option, but an urgent need if we want to influence the current course of the socio-environmental crises. From this premise, the group reflected on the difficulty, and at the same time the urgency, of integrating other knowledge systems into research processes traditionally based on the scientific method. For this group, innovation was conceptualized collectively, as a rethinking of the entire research process: from the formulation of the questions, through the methods and tools, to the dissemination strategies. The importance of innovating both in the use of technologies to study ecological changes was highlighted as was the ways of communicating results so that they are understandable and useful to the people and communities with whom they work.

The third group to present focused its discussion on collaboration and the ontological dimension of innovation. It was argued that innovating implies rethinking the very meaning of research and the way in which the Amazon is conceived, not as an object of study, but as a living system. From this perspective, local communities must be recognized as research subjects with greater symmetrical and horizontal relationships. This starts from the moment when research questions are defined. The importance of focusing on research processes was underlined, so that they lead to the generation of key learning for the appropriation of knowledge. Likewise, the need to transform academic training, still very closed and focused on publication logics, was debated, proposing the

idea of "de-innovating": recognizing that science is only one of many ways of knowing, and that innovating can mean leaving the scientific framework, sharing knowledge in unwritten ways, and establishing dialogues between different ways of existing and understanding the world. Although this group recognized the relevance of Indigenous knowledge in the dialogue of knowledge, it highlighted the importance of including other knowledge systems that go beyond the Indigenous. This group's reflections on innovation included the learning, experiences, and knowledge of peasant, settler and urban populations, since they are also an important part of the demographic composition of the Amazon.

Figure 9. Innovation Working Group

For the fourth group, innovation was understood as an attitude and a sustained practice of curiosity aimed at solving problems or achieving concrete results. The importance of constantly questioning what questions are asked, for whom, with whom, and for what purpose was highlighted. From this reflection arose the notion of relevance: innovation implies recognizing local cosmologies and realities and thinking outside the usual scientific frameworks. It was highlighted that, in some cases, innovation may consist of returning to ancestral or traditional practices, especially when external technological solutions do not fit local contexts. The importance of taking care of the flows of knowledge was also pointed out, prioritizing listening and learning from the communities, rather than a one-way transmission of knowledge.

The next group addressed innovation from a diversity of knowledge and the understanding of the territory as a multidimensional system. Emphasis was placed on interdisciplinarity and the need to understand how technologies are inserted and transform territories. Linear logics of thought were

questioned, proposing instead more dynamic and relational visions of change. The discussion highlighted the importance of articulating, rather than forcibly uniting, different systems of knowledge, reducing epistemological asymmetries. Ethical dimensions of innovation were also addressed, such as the protection of knowledge and the responsible use of data. Finally, it was highlighted that many innovative practices arise from the precariousness and inequality that exists in many of the countries with Amazonian territory, and that recovering knowledge from the past can be key to facing current and future challenges associated with socio-environmental crises.

For the sixth group to present, the conversation was organized around how and why innovation is made. It was stated that all innovation must be built on existing knowledge, recognizing the contributions of the past. Innovation was described as an uncertain process, involving trial and error, sensitivity, and patience. It was pointed out that innovation does not always mean creating new technologies, but also recovering, understanding, and deepening knowledge that is being lost. The role of modern technology was critically discussed, noting that many of these technological advances that are relied upon for research also contribute to the degradation of the Amazon. Identifying information gaps, deepening knowledge about ecological and social interactions, and improving forms of dissemination to different audiences were identified as key paths of innovation. This group also took up the idea of the Amazon as a living organism and the need to "decompose" its complexity in order to understand and act on it.

Figure 10. Working group exchanging ideas on innovation

The last group to present defined innovation as the generation of new ideas, methods and approaches that allow adaptation to changing conditions. The need to connect Indigenous and scientific knowledge to face these changes jointly was highlighted. For them too, innovation was

understood as a continuous process of trial and error, aimed at improving people's lives and the conservation of species. It was also stressed that, in many cases, more than innovating, it is about reassessing and integrating local knowledge that is already part of the daily practices of research and management within the territory.

At the end of the plenary, some people reflected on what they learned by listening to their peers from other groups. Each account deepened and stressed the previous discussions, broadening the debate on innovation beyond the methodological or technological. The need to create bridges between disciplines with different epistemological frameworks was underlined, as well as to question the role of technology in the definition of research agendas and in the production of knowledge. Also raised were ethical and political concerns related to the uses of information, the risks of innovating without an in-depth contextual analysis and the need to demystify certain knowledge without delegitimizing it and recognizing the ecological changes underway.

Finally, the question of innovation timelines was put at the center, inviting reflection on who innovates, for whom and under what time horizons, especially in the context of the conservation of the Amazon. The table below presents a synthesis of the main reflections raised by the working groups.

Table 3. Joint reflections on innovation in research processes

Key theme	Description
Innovation as a situated, temporary, and adaptive process	Innovation is understood as a process deeply anchored in the territory and its ecological and social dynamics, sensitive to the rhythms of nature and people. It implies recognizing long time horizons typical of conservation, in tension with the logic of acceleration that characterizes many contemporary innovations and the time horizon of project financing.
Comprehensive rethinking of the research process	Innovation means critically reviewing the entire research process: from the epistemological frameworks that guide the questions, to the methods, tools, analyses and forms of dissemination. This includes questioning innovation "for innovation's sake" and assessing its potential social, political, and environmental effects.
Articulation of multiple disciplines and knowledge systems	Innovation requires creating connections between biological, social, and economic sciences, recognizing their different philosophical and methodological frameworks. It also implies articulating scientific knowledge with Indigenous, peasant, local, and urban knowledge, reducing epistemological asymmetries and promoting more horizontal relationships.
Ambivalent role of technology	Technologies can open up new research agendas and make previously marginal problems visible, but they can also generate risks if the contexts of use, the actors involved, and the ethical and political implications are not considered. Innovation implies critically reflecting on what, how, and for whom technologies are used.

Ethics, power and political incidence of knowledge	Innovation is traversed by power relations: who sets agendas, who controls data, who benefits from the information generated, and how this affects decision-making. The need to think of research as a process with political implications is underlined and to assume that responsibilities extend beyond the academic field.
Amazon as a living, relational, and diverse system	The Amazon is conceived as a living and multidimensional system, whose understanding requires relational, non-linear approaches that are open to uncertainty. Innovation can mean recovering knowledge from the past, learning from experience, and accepting trial and error as a constituent part of knowledge processes.

2.2. Impact on conservation research in the Amazon

The following are the main contributions of each group, presented in plenary, to the second guiding question: *What makes research in the Amazon have an impact?*

For the first group that presented in plenary, the discussion revolved around the idea that all research generates impact, regardless of its scale or visibility, and that this impact should be understood as a gradual and cumulative process. It was pointed out that the impact increases to the extent that a sustained presence is maintained in the territory. From this perspective, the importance of defining clear goals was highlighted, as well as carrying out a mapping of actors that allows identifying interests and expectations, and formulating research questions that are relevant to the people involved. Likewise, the need to diversify dissemination products was underlined, recognizing the centrality of orality, and to build routes that connect research with advocacy on environmental policies. Impact was also understood as something that manifests itself in a differentiated way depending on the focus of the work, whether in species, ecosystems, or specific problems of the territory.

The discussion of the next group led the participants to make a list of criteria where they define that a research project has an impact if:

1. It generates concrete benefits for communities, considering differences in gender, age, and the diversity of social actors
2. A process of co-creation of the research is carried out taking into account intersectionality.
3. It values and legitimizes traditional knowledge through more horizontal exchanges of knowledge.
4. There is an appropriate and common use of technology.
5. It is sustainable in terms of financing.

The presentation of the subsequent group reiterated that research always has an impact, whether positive, negative, individual, or collective. From this perspective, the importance of maintaining an openness to local interests was underlined, which allows a more equitable distribution of the benefits of research. The involvement of Indigenous peoples in research processes was identified as a key factor to strengthen local autonomy and improve decision-making, as well as to produce more relevant and contextualized scientific results.

Figure 11. Working group exchanging ideas on impacts on the research process

From a reflection initially anchored in the academic field, the fourth group problematized the idea that impact is measured only through scientific publications. The conversation drifted towards an understanding of impact as something that is built throughout the entire research process, from the early stages of formulation and context analysis to implementation and monitoring. It was highlighted that the early involvement of different actors who could collaborate, or may be impacted by such research, contributes to building networks of trust that strengthen the research process. In this space, different types of impact were also distinguished, including not only those that can be measured rationally or technically, but also emotional impact, understood as a tangible result that, although rarely visible in formal indicators, can be decisive for conservation. The need to deepen what it means to co-construct knowledge was also raised, and to recognize the role of emotions as a relevant component in advocacy processes.

The fifth group emphasized reflecting on the question of who is the research for? It was highlighted that local actors who reside where activities are carried out must participate throughout the process. They noted that the impact is not limited to the production of academic results, but also the extent to which research benefits reach the most local levels. The importance of making knowledge, not just scientific knowledge, visible was underlined, as was recognizing that there are territories where scientific research has historically been absent, which also constitutes a form of impact. It was also mentioned that working with species or resources relevant to communities usually facilitates the appropriation of results, especially when they are disseminated in local languages.

Finally, the last group focused its discussion on the co-creation and co-production of knowledge based on multiple experiences and interpretations of the world, insisting on the need for these contributions to be recognized. Research impact was also understood in terms of improvements in quality of life, such as the generation of income associated with conservation or changes towards more sustainable ways of life. It was pointed out that research can generate visibility and attention

to territories, and that tools such as monitoring technologies arouse interest and emotions among those who inhabit these spaces, strengthening their link with research and conservation processes.

Table 4 briefly presents the main reflections of the working groups.

Table 4. Joint reflections on the impact on research

Thematic axis	Description
Impact as a situated, long-term process	Research impact was understood as a gradual, cumulative process closely linked to permanence in the territory. It is built over time and can manifest itself at different scales, from specific changes to broader transformations in ecosystems and social dynamics.
Territorial relevance and definition of objectives	Research generates impact when it starts from clear goals and questions relevant to local contexts. This involves mapping actors, recognizing interests and expectations, and adapting the research design to the social, ecological, and political realities of each territory.
Co-creation, participation and governance	Research impact is strengthened when research is carried out in a participatory manner, incorporating local and Indigenous communities as central actors in the production of knowledge. These processes favor autonomy, the appropriation of results, and the construction of fairer and more effective governance arrangements.
Multiple impact dimensions	It was recognized that impact is not limited to technical or academic outcomes, but includes social, emotional, cultural, and relational dimensions. These dimensions, although difficult to measure, have a decisive influence on conservation processes and incidence.
Communication, ownership, and sustainability	The diversification of dissemination products, the responsible use of technologies, and the valorization of non-scientific knowledge facilitate the appropriation of knowledge. Research impact also depends on an ability to sustain research processes over time, both through financing and concrete benefits for the communities.

2.3. Inclusion in conservation research in the Amazon

After a general recap of the exercises carried out during the morning, the group addressed the third and final question of the day on inclusivity in research. It was pointed out that this issue had already appeared in a transversal way in the previous discussions, and that in this space it would be addressed directly. Unlike the previous questions, this reflection was not worked on individually, but exclusively through discussions in small groups, which again, later shared their main ideas in plenary.

The first group to present focused its reflection on the importance of diversity and accessibility as pillars of inclusive research. The need to disseminate results in languages other than English and in different formats was highlighted, thus avoiding that knowledge is restricted to technical or

academic languages. Likewise, the relevance of forming diverse work teams, including women, young people, adults, and different social sectors was highlighted, as was thinking about the benefits of research from a collective logic. Inclusivity was associated with less hierarchical and more horizontal processes, with open communication and dialogue, involving schools, public institutions and other local actors. In this framework, the relationship of inclusion with the equitable distribution of the benefits derived from the projects was also discussed.

The next group directly problematized the use of the term "inclusion", pointing out that it can reproduce power relations by assuming that there is a someone who decides who is included and at what time. Instead, the importance of dialogue, horizontality, active listening, and co-creation of research processes was emphasized. Experiences were shared that highlighted the need to have the explicit consent of the participants and to recognize them as a central part of the research process, including their presence in the final products. Likewise, the importance of returning the information generated to those who made contributions throughout the research process was highlighted, so that this information can be validated and appropriated by the communities.

The third group addressed inclusivity from the notion of equity, pointing out that talking about inclusion implies recognizing pre-existing inequalities. It was insisted that co-creation processes must be accompanied by dissemination strategies appropriate to local contexts, privileging visual, graphic, and open access formats, which do not generate new barriers. Inclusivity was also associated with tangible and intangible benefits for communities, such as training processes and strengthening local capacities. In this space, the importance of recognizing the time and work of the people who participate directly in the research was underlined, as well as the need for transparency in the conditions of collaboration, including times, responsibilities, and compensations. Regulatory frameworks and safeguards aimed at protecting traditional knowledge and preventing its appropriation or commodification were also mentioned.

Figure 12. Working group exchanging ideas on inclusion in the research process

The discussion of the fourth group revolved around the enabling conditions for inclusion. It was pointed out that inclusion cannot occur without safe spaces, transparency, and clear communication from the beginning of the process. Multiple barriers to achieving inclusion were identified, such as language (understood in both linguistic and technical terms), lack of spaces to ask questions, and the tendency to assume homogeneity in contexts that are actually profoundly diverse. The need to go beyond checklists or formal quotas was raised, promoting effective and contextualized participation so that it is present at all times in which the research is carried out. In this sense, the role of gender protocols and biocultural research was discussed, which must go a step further from standard government requirements. This group also mentioned recent changes in funding schemes, where donors are directing resources directly to local communities. In this sense, they foresee a change in the relations between these communities, researchers, and NGOs, since in the near future, it will be the communities themselves who decide what research is relevant, inverting the traditional logics of inclusion.

The fifth group emphasized that inclusivity requires time, resources, and willingness to learn, and that it cannot be imposed in an accelerated or instrumental way. The coexistence of multiple forms of knowledge and the need to recognize them without placing them in a hierarchy were highlighted. Intersectionality was also addressed as a long-term process, which cannot be reduced to quotas or invasive interventions, especially in contexts with complex social structures. Paternalistic practices and compensation schemes were critically discussed, which are already installed in the region with the presence, for example, of oil companies, which can distort relations between actors. This group emphasized the importance of data governance and ensuring that the information generated is returned, understood, and accessible to communities. In the discussion it was mentioned that for there to be inclusion, there must be curiosity and a desire to learn from the parties involved. Therefore, when working with local communities, it is important to know their interests before imposing external research agendas. Finally, inclusion was understood as an indispensable condition to generate real impact for conservation.

Finally, the last group stated that inclusivity depends on the type of project, the discipline, and the design of the research itself. It was pointed out that, in many cases, inclusion is introduced in a forced and tardy manner, rather than being thought of from the beginning. Examples were discussed showing how gender dynamics, productive roles, schedules, and local routines directly influence the possibility of effective participation. The importance of free, prior, and informed consent was also underlined, and the discussion was broadened to topics such as authorship, intellectual recognition, and participation in subsequent outputs, including publications and possible patents. From this perspective, inclusivity was understood as an open, situated, and negotiated process, rather than as a closed or universal goal.

Table 5 summarizes the main reflections made in the working groups.

Table 5. Synthesis of joint reflections on inclusion in the research process

Thematic axis	Description
Equity and redistribution of benefits	Inclusivity is associated with fairer relationships between those who research and those who participate in the research. This implies recognizing local rhythms, work, and contributions, as well as a more equitable distribution of economic and non-economic benefits, avoiding extractive or paternalistic schemes.
Co-creation and horizontality	Inclusive research is built through processes of dialogue, listening, and co-creation, where communities are not only sources of information, but central actors in the design, development, and validation of knowledge. Hierarchical structures are questioned and more horizontal relationships are promoted.
Language, communication, and accessibility	Inclusivity requires overcoming linguistic and technical barriers through the use of multiple languages, accessible formats, and outreach strategies to different audiences. Open access and cultural appropriateness of research products are key to avoiding further exclusions.
Context, timetables, and enabling conditions	Being inclusive implies recognizing the diversity of social and cultural contexts, as well as local rhythms, schedules and priorities. Building trust demands time, flexibility, and resources, and cannot be limited to formal demands or checklists.
Consent, transparency, and knowledge governance	Inclusivity is linked to ethical practices such as free, prior, and informed consent, clarity on conditions of participation, and the return of results. It also includes the protection of traditional knowledge, data governance, and recognition in authorship and future developments.

3. Harvesting perspectives from the three I's

The closing period of the second day was dedicated to an integrative reflection by the thematic leaders of the workshop, who resumed the day's discussions on innovation, impact and inclusivity in research for the conservation of the Amazon.

First, the idea of innovating and de-innovating was highlighted as a central axis. This led to thinking of innovation not only as the creation of something new, but also as the ability to go back to the past, review previous experiences, and learn from processes that have already occurred. This temporal perspective was articulated with a recurrent concern about the speed of innovations, questioning the accelerated rhythms from which many interventions in Amazonian contexts tend to be proposed. The need to broaden dialogue protagonists was also underlined, incorporating all actors that make up nature and recognizing it as a living organism. In this framework, it was pointed out that innovation does not always arise from ideal contexts, but that precarity itself can generate creative forms of innovation, especially in historically marginalized territories.

Another central reflection revolved around the question: What kind of innovation is being sought? If it is technological, political, ontological, or other? What lessons about innovation emerge from the territories? This led to key questions about who and with whom to innovate, as well as about the role of public and private institutions in these processes.

The importance of thinking of innovation as an integral process, which starts from research planning and extends to the dissemination of information, insisting on early decisions on what information will be shared, how it will be done, and what the implications of information disclosure may be in terms of impact and the balance of territorial dynamics. In this sense, it was proposed to understand innovation as a multidimensional system, which does not fragment humans from nature, which incorporates diverse philosophical perspectives, which considers the impacts on the communities involved, and which is based on respect for all forms of life. Temporality, patience, and the recognition of emotions were pointed out as key elements to integrate innovation into the territories and the daily lives of those who inhabit them.

Figure 13. Thematic leaders sharing their reflections

During the final reflection, the three workshop concepts featured - innovation, impact and inclusivity - were taken up together. It was highlighted that although formulated differently, the answers converge and are nourished by the personal and professional experiences of those who conduct research in the Amazon. Elevated was the importance of each person constantly asking themselves in their daily research efforts if their work is having an impact and if it is really being inclusive.

The ongoing tension between meeting donor requirements and at the same time, developing research that is relevant, inclusive, and with real impact was also recognized. In this context, it was emphasized that inclusivity is not limited to the socialization of results, but implies guaranteeing participation throughout the entire process, from research design to project closure. Likewise, the relevance of considering the temporal and spatial scales of research impact was highlighted, especially in a region as large and diverse as the Amazon. Finally, it was pointed out that issues such as intellectual rights directly intersect with discussions on impact and inclusiveness and require deeper reflection. The idea that truly inclusive research has greater possibilities of generating impact was raised, inviting individual and collective reflection on research practices. The Amazon was described, at the same time, as a blessing and a challenge, a territory that demands critical, ethical, and deeply committed inquiry.

DAY 3: SHARED EXPERIENCES

To close the activities of the second day, each individual attendee was challenged to create a poster that would be presented the next day. This activity invited each participant to reflect in a situated way on their own research practice and to identify how their work could be considered innovative.

Innovation was understood in a broad way: it could be related to the place where research is carried out, to the methodologies used, types of collaboration established with different actors, to the use of technologies, or to combinations of these elements. In addition, poster creators were asked to make explicit how this research generated impact and how it was inclusive.

To guide poster construction, a series of common guidelines were shared. Each poster had to include a title or topic, a brief introduction about the project, the research question(s) or its purpose, the place where it is developed, the methods used, and an explicit reflection on the ways in which the research presented was innovative, impactful, and promoted inclusivity.

Figure 14. Workshop participant of the workshop making their poster to present their research

On the morning of the 3rd day, a space was allocated for socialization of the posters. The participants were invited to locate their work in an open area near the main room where the workshop had taken place. Once the posters were installed, the group split in two. At first, half of the people remained next to their poster to present it, while the other half walked around the space, listening to the explanations of their colleagues.

During this “tour”, poster visitors were asked to write their name on at least two of them, using sticky notes, as a way to signal interest and leave open the possibility of establishing subsequent contact to delve more deeply into the topics presented. This gesture sought to promote exchange, mutual recognition, and the creation of possible links beyond the workshop space.

After about an hour, the roles were reversed. Those who had initially been visiting the posters went to stand in front of theirs to exhibit them, while the rest of the group took the tour. In this way, all people had the opportunity both to present their work and to learn in detail about the research experiences of others. This resulted in a dynamic and horizontal format that privileged direct conversation and peer exchange.

MANEJO COMUNITARIO DEL FUEGO ANDES-AMAZONÍA

QUEMA AGRÍCOLA
Otras causas
Si no se controla
↓
INCENDIO FORESTAL

- 100-200 familias
- agricultura familiar
- uso del fuego
- limpiar chacra
- abrir nuevas chacras
- pastos para ganado
- eliminar malezas y desechos agrícolas

MÉTODOS

- entrevistas
- observación participante
- grupos y grupos de trabajo
- Si metodología cuantitativa/agrícola

Innovador

- enfoque de manejo integrado del fuego

Área Impacto

- esfuerzos de comunicación de diversos

Inclusiva

- facilitadores de talleres a comunidad
- perspectiva de mayores y jóvenes sobre cambio
- Co-que: intérprete/facilitador

Vanessa Luna

Ciencia para la Toma de decisiones sobre áreas protegidas

Objetivo/proósito: Mejorar el acceso y uso de la ciencia académica en las decisiones sobre AP de la Amazonia

Dónde: Madre de Dios y Loreto

Métodos:

- 1. Innovadora: Ciencia-políticas ANP
- 2. Inclusiva: gestores académicos, académicos y regionales
- 3. Integrar la evidencia en las políticas

CRISTINA MIRANDA

"DE PROBLEMA A VALIDACIÓN EN 90 MINUTOS: Design Thinking + IA"

Introducción: JAVIER

Propósito: Aplicar un proceso Inclusivo, ágil y basado en datos que permita obtener validaciones y prototipos

¿Dónde? En Territorio

Innovadora: Enfoque IA, con Design Thinking

DE Impacto: Mejora el mundo de columnas y reduce la mortalidad.

Inclusivo: usable x jóvenes, comunidades y change-makers sin mayores conocimientos

ARMADILLOS DE COLOMBIA

- 7/24 especies
- 3 SP. Condición de Amenaza
- Región Orinoquía

Perdida de hábitat → Quemas

Cadenas Comerciales → Perros

Ayoajimidos → Zoonosis

Atiopesilamentos → monocultivos

¿Cuál es la ecología poblacional y cómo mitigar las amenazas para su conservación?

Innovative: Métodos poco usuales. Estudiar un animal fosorial. Retoma conocimiento ancestral/cultural

Impactfull: Coejecución con Comunidades Incentivos

Inclusiva: Equidad de género, todos las edades, Promueve bienestar

Carlos Aya

MUDANÇAS AMBIENTAIS: QUAIS SEUS EFEITOS NAS COMUNIDADES HUMANAS E ANIMAIS?

Armadillos ferozes

COMUNIDADES RIBEIRINHAS

RAP: Inventários RAPidos

LIDAR: Estrutura da Floresta

AFs: Armadillos, Ratos e Raposas (Sapo & Bexiga)

Pesquisadores Locais

QUAIS ÁREAS ESTÃO SAUVÁVEIS?

QUAIS ANIMAIS ESTÃO DESAPARECENDO?

QUAIS PRINCIPAIS PRESSÕES?

QUAIS AMBIENTES ESTÃO VULNERÁVEIS?

ONDE A CAÇA TEM MAIOR IMPACTO?

ONDE O DESMATAAMENTO É MAIOR?

DADOS → **DIAGNÓSTICO**

Mapeio territorial, Comunicação de espécies, Segurança alimentar

Material informativo, Fortalecimento de vínculos, Retorno de conhecimento

Acuerdos Locales de Pesca

Introducción: los acuerdos locales de pesca en el Ampiyacu son procesos de gobernanza local reconocidos a nivel regional en Loreto. Promueven la buena gobernanza del recurso pesquero que se ha desarrollado por 15 años.

Propósito a d?

- * Diagnóstico de los acuerdos (cuáles funcionan y no) como funcionan...
- * ¿Cuál es la percepción de los beneficiarios de los acuerdos? (comunidades y otras acciones)
- * Analizar los gaps de investigación. Si monitorio biológico y conectarlo con percepciones

Metodos: Entrevistas, Talleres comunitarios, Análisis de datos, Encuestas, etc.

¿Dónde? Quebrada del Ampiyacu, 14 comunidades

Innovación, Impacto e Inclusión: Gobernanza, Sostenibilidad, etc.

Figure 15. Examples of posters presented at the workshop

1. Emerging reflections from the poster fair

At the end of the two poster presentation shifts, the attendees met again to collectively reflect on the exercise. The facilitator proposed an open question aimed at inquiring about the meaning of the activity and what it had mobilized in the participants. From this invitation, reflections emerged that allowed the exercise to be read beyond the presentation of individual results.

Figure 16. Poster presentation round

One of the ideas that ran through several reflections was that the poster exercise functioned as a space to activate connections: connections between people, between topics, between territories, and between ways of doing research. The tour of the posters allowed us to learn about the different approaches to conservation through a diversity of research practices, as well as the wealth of experiences that coexist in a large and heterogeneous territory such as the Amazon.

For several people, this recognition was not only informative, but also relational. It allowed them to identify possible complementarities, affinities, and opportunities for joint work. Repeatedly, it was pointed out that the exercise led to a reflection on the research practice itself. Having to synthesize a project in a visual format and explain it to people who were not necessarily specialists forced us to stop, organize ideas, and return to the questions posed the day before about innovation, impact and inclusivity.

In this process, some people recognized gaps, tensions or aspects that could be strengthened, as well as the possibility of adjusting ongoing projects to be more coherent with the three I's. In this sense, the poster operated as a device for self-evaluation and situated learning. Seeing so many

initiatives brought together made it possible to measure how many things are happening simultaneously, and at the same time, the limited visibility these activities can have if there are no spaces for exchange. This led to reflection on open access to information, on how to make data and research results really inform decision-making, and on the need to close the gap between knowledge production and advocacy. The value of the analogue format was also highlighted.

The use of hand-crafted posters, drawings, and visual resources was considered a departure from comfort zones in the face of more common digital presentations. Several participants highlighted that this format favored recall, leisurely conversation, and the transmission of ideas in a more accessible way. The materiality of the poster helped the information to last beyond the immediate moment of the exhibition and facilitated face-to-face exchange. Another axis that emerged strongly was that of passion and commitment.

As they went through the posters, several people pointed out that what struck them most was not only the technical content of the projects, but the way in which those who presented them talked about their work. The emotion, enthusiasm, and bond with the territories and people involved were read as clear signs of commitment, and as a valuable and often invisible component in research processes.

The discussion also opened critical questions about the structural conditions of research, particularly within academia. It was mentioned that there are few incentives to involve non-academic actors, as their engagement is usually perceived as high cost in terms of time, resources, and institutional recognition. From this, the concern arose about how to create conditions that value and promote more collaborative practices, without these depending solely on individual motivation. Several participants emphasized the democratization of information and knowledge.

Finally, the exercise was interpreted as an opportunity for participants to take away ideas and inspiration. Some people pointed out that certain posters opened up new questions, showed them tools or approaches that they did not know, or allowed them to think about research from different scales, languages, and sensibilities. Beyond choosing one or two specific posters, the value of the set was highlighted: the feeling that the posters were "alive", that they dialogued with each other, and that they reflected shared searches around how to investigate in a more innovative, inclusive, and impactful way. The closing raised an idea that had already appeared in previous discussions: that impact should not be a final addition to the research, but an integrated dimension from the beginning of the process. In this sense, the exercise of the posters not only allowed us to show what each person does, but also to reopen questions about how and for what research is done, and with whom those paths are built.

2. Discussion on ethics in the research process

After lunch, a new workspace was opened aimed at discussing ethical issues in research, resuming previous conversations and the poster exercise. The facilitators proposed a dynamic based on seven stages of the research process, which were arranged on flip charts around the room:

- 1) Group formation and definition of research questions
- 2) Project design
- 3) Data collection
- 4) Analysis
- 5) Data interpretation
- 6) Dissemination of results
- 7) Data ownership

Attendees were asked to choose one of these stages. To make their selection, they were asked to reflect on their past experiences and identify any ethical dilemmas they have had to face that may be related to or framed in some of these stages of the research process. From this choice, people were grouped according to the selected stage, sharing concrete examples and ways to deal with them. During the introduction of the activity, it was pointed out that, although there are general guides and guidelines on research ethics, the purpose of this space was to exchange situated experiences, focused on how these dilemmas are manifested and managed in the daily practice of research projects.

The groups had approximately half an hour to discuss their experiences, highlight the ethical considerations involved, the decisions they had to make in each case, and select one or two situations to share in plenary. One aspect that drew attention during the dynamic was that no one approached the flip charts corresponding to the stages of project design, analysis, and data interpretation, which opened questions about how and at what moments of the research process ethical dilemmas are usually identified, or not. Once the group work was finished, the plenary space began. The following are the experiences shared by the groups in which participants congregated, organized according to the stages of the research process that were discussed.

Stage 1. Group formation and definition of research questions

The group that worked on this stage of the research process presented three experiences that demonstrated ethical dilemmas associated with the moment in which the research questions are formulated, and the actors involved are defined. It was highlighted that this is a critical point, since it establishes the bases of the research process and the relationships that sustain it.

The first case was related to a study on the conservation of a species of Amazonian turtle that, on a regional scale, has healthy populations, but in a specific park it seemed to be being overexploited by the indigenous community that inhabits the area. The research was initially aimed at analyzing food consumption patterns, but, as the work progressed, questions arose from the communities about the legitimacy of the study and its results. It was stated that scientists were prioritizing the conservation of the species without considering local food needs and practices, including the nutritional value of eggs for people's diets. Faced with this scenario, the decision was made to stop the project, despite having solid data, and not continue until it could be reopened collectively, integrating Indigenous communities, park authorities and scientists from different disciplines. The pandemic prevented this process from resuming, but the decision to pause the study was understood as a way of assuming the ethical dilemma from the beginning of the research.

The second case focused on an Amazon-scale citizen science project designed to answer an ambitious question about fish migration. Although the research question was considered pertinent, it was recognized that it had been formulated by a scientific elite, without the participation of those who would later be summoned as citizen scientists, including local and indigenous researchers from different parts of the basin. This exclusion at the formulation stage generated tensions, especially when it was evident that participation in data collection was expected, but not in the definition of the questions. Part of the conflict was resolved because the breadth of the question allowed different actors to join in, providing data that also responded to local and personal interests, although the case left open the reflection on who defines the questions and from where the research is constructed.

The third case addressed archaeological research and the very definition of what is considered evidence. In this process, it was decided to start the work not with external specialists, but with people from the local communities who have a deep knowledge of the territory, fauna, and flora. From this example, it was evident that for the communities, the identification of ancient settlements does not necessarily involve material ruins, but rather specific associations of vegetation linked to ancient uses of the territory. These associations, rather than archaeological objects, are read as indicators of past occupations. From this perspective, the extraction of cultural material from its context was rejected, and methodologies that would allow archaeological sites to be recognized without altering or displacing objects were chosen. This experience highlighted the importance of recognizing other criteria of validity and other forms of knowledge from the very moment the research question is defined.

Together, the three cases show how the stage of forming groups and defining questions is essential to anticipate and manage ethical dilemmas. The decisions made at this early stage not only condition the trajectory of the project, but also mark the possibility of generating positive social impacts throughout the research process.

Stage 3. Data collection

During the discussion on data collection, the groups presented various experiences that reflected the multiplicity of ethical dilemmas that emerge at this stage of the research. It was evident that this moment not only involves technical decisions about how the data is obtained, but also considerations about safety, respect, confidentiality, and well-being, both of the people and animals involved.

A first set of reflections focused on the human and social aspects of data collection. It was noted that research teams are often culturally and geographically diverse, and that this diversity can lead to tensions and conflicts related to behavior during activities, gender, or harassment. To address these risks, some groups have implemented codes of conduct that establish clear rules of coexistence and respect for peers and local communities. These rules include agreements on safety, the number of people working in teams, and behavioral guidelines that guarantee harmonious coexistence without limiting the freedom of individual team members.

At the same time, it was discussed how ethics in data collection go beyond compliance with institutional protocols. For example, when working with local communities, it is necessary to

ensure transparency and clarity about research objectives, incentives for participation, and expectations about the confidentiality of information. This implies not only protecting the research team members, but also recognizing their rights and schedules, respecting their knowledge and ways of interacting with the territory.

Another important focus of thought revolved around ethics in animal data collection. Participants noted that different methodologies can generate stress or risk for animals and that these implications should be discussed beforehand among researchers. The need to negotiate research protocols according to the local context was highlighted, as international standards are not always applicable or appropriate in other countries. This dialogue also includes the management of genetic material, biosecurity, and the use of technologies such as camera traps, which can indirectly affect the behavior of people and animals in the territory.

Participants discussed the importance of confidentiality and responsible disclosure of data. Cases of viral camera trap photos and the handling of genetic information highlighted that ethical risks are not limited to the internal procedures of the team, but extend to how the data can affect communities, species and ecosystems. In relation to the collection of data on animals, the need to consider the indirect impacts of research was noted. For example, a participant mentioned a study of camera traps in Asian forests that changed the behavior of local people. Women altered their routes, avoided passing by the cameras with children, and modified their daily behaviors. This example illustrates how the presence of monitoring instruments can influence communities and the importance of anticipating these effects in the design of protocols.

Figure 17. Participants discussing ethical dilemmas at the time of data collection

Finally, the administrative and regulatory difficulties faced by researchers in different countries were mentioned, which can affect the implementation of ethical protocols, especially in contexts where regulations are inconsistent or bureaucratic. Taken together, the shared experiences reflect

that data collection is a stage in which responsibility towards people, communities, and biodiversity converge. Ethical decisions made at this time not only protect those involved, but also strengthen the quality, validity and impact of research, demonstrating that ethics must be integrated as an active and ongoing component of fieldwork.

Stage 6. Dissemination of results

Workshop attendees agreed that it is essential to establish an early dialogue with all people involved, especially on sensitive issues such as authorship, rights to research products, and the way information is communicated. However, it was also recognized that this is often not possible from the beginning and dilemmas are resolved in the course of the project. Several examples were shared that illustrate these challenges.

In one case, it was necessary to decide how to include local collaborators in the authorship of a chapter that addressed socio-environmental problems; The proposed solution was to make explicit the contribution of each person in a footnote, acknowledging participation without attributing conclusions to those who had not reviewed the final text.

Another example involved research on musical bamboos, where the community preferred not to participate in a scientific publication because they considered that the paper's content was far from their cultural context. However, they did want to engage in broader, culturally relevant outreach processes. Producing an audiovisual piece was also discussed, in which they decided to transfer economic rights of the film to an external company to ensure that the short film had greater reach, even if that meant losing control over it. This example evidenced the tension between visibility, impact, and ownership of results.

A recurring theme was the need for clarity on disclosure standards, both legal and cultural. Institutional and national protocols exist, but many Indigenous communities have their own processes and rules about what can be researched and disseminated, as well as the appropriate places and times for it. This implies that ethics in disclosure cannot be limited to complying with formal rules. It requires negotiation, respect, and flexibility in the face of prior agreements and community autonomy. Overall, the reports showed that results dissemination is not a neutral act, but an ethical process that combines respect for people, recognition of their contributions, and attention to the cultural, political, and legal context in which the research is carried out.

Stage 7. Data ownership

The discussion of data ownership highlighted the importance of addressing this important issue from the beginning of any research and of reviewing it continuously throughout the project. Several illustrative examples were presented.

One of the participants shared the practices used by a Colombian research institute, where the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) and CARE (Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, Ethics) principles are implemented for data management. Although the experience of the institute has been positive, it was recognized that these principles must be complemented by specific agreements with local actors, adapted to each context. Thus, in

collaboration with an Indigenous reservation in Colombia, it was circumscribed that the reservation itself is the publisher of the data in the national biodiversity information system, deciding what information is published and what is kept confidential. This process is developed step by step in constant accompaniment with the Institute's team of researchers and is adjusted to the cultural and regulatory particularities of the community.

Another example came from a project in Guyana with camera traps, where the community signed a written permission that established how data would be shared, authorship rules, and expectations of participation. During the discussion, questions arose about the meaning of co-ownership of data and how to balance transparency with the protection of sensitive information, such as the location of vulnerable species. Technological mechanisms were also implemented to enable a deferred release of certain data, respecting community decisions and animal safety.

A third example was a regional database on fishery resources, managed in collaboration with an international academic institution. This database operates under an open contributory model but adapted to guarantee data security and traceability. Mechanisms are currently being developed to recognize the authorship of those who collect and contribute data, so that credit and visibility of participating researchers and communities are explicit.

Taken together, these cases showed that data ownership cannot be defined in a uniform way. It requires clear agreements, constant negotiation, adaptation to local contexts, and ethical consideration of community and participant rights. It also shows that co-ownership and responsible data management are essential to strengthen trust, transparency, and collaboration in research.

Table 6 summarizes the main ethical dilemmas presented by participants during each of the stages of the research.

Table 6. Ethical dilemmas at different stages of the research process

Stage of the investigation	Ethical dilemmas identified	Key learnings / Considerations
Group formation and question definition	Exclusion of local actors, legitimacy of research, respect for traditional knowledge	The formulation of questions should include all relevant actors. Stopping or adjusting the investigation is a form of respect and legitimacy.
Data collection	Conflicts between researchers, harassment, respect for communities, animal welfare, biopiracy, confidentiality, biosecurity	Ethics goes beyond written protocols. Clear rules of respect and security strengthen the quality of data and coexistence. Adapting protocols according to the local context is key.

Dissemination of results	Authorship, visibility of local contributions, cultural sensitivity of information	Dialogue from the beginning about authorship and forms of dissemination. Ethical behavior requires flexibility and adaptation according to the sensitivity of information and agreements with communities.
Data ownership	Co-ownership, data rights, responsible publishing, protection of sensitive information	Discuss data ownership from the start. Establish clear agreements for co-ownership, permits, and acknowledgment of contributions. Adapt practices to cultural and legal contexts.

DAY 4: LESSONS LEARNED AND COLLECTIVE NEXT STEPS

The day began with an open-ended question from the facilitator, asking where in the Amazon would they take others to visit. The responses covered very diverse territories, from cloud forests and blackwater rivers to river beaches, Indigenous reserves and protected areas. However, the responses also shared common elements: a deep emotional connection with the landscapes, the richness of biodiversity (birds, primates, and large mammals), the presence of water as the axis of the territory, and the historical and cultural memory of the places. Several people highlighted both the natural beauty and conservation challenges, as well as the spiritual and community value of these spaces.

Figure 18. Participants during activity to start the last day of the workshop

1. Lessons learned

After reviewing the general objectives of the workshop and the agenda for the day, the facilitator gave instructions for the next activity. Each attendee had five minutes to individually answer the question: *What is one realization that you take away from these three days that will make your work more innovative, have more impact, and be inclusive?* Subsequently, a wider space was opened for people to group by country and share their reflections.

Bolivia:

The Bolivian group highlighted the importance of the proper and ethical use of technology, such as camera traps, especially for their ability to show in real time what is happening in the forest. They also highlighted how research is strengthened when working in an interdisciplinary way,

even within the social sciences themselves. They mentioned that in their country there is a strong limitation in human resources, with few doctoral students and multiple shortcomings in university education, as well as the absence of institutions that formalize the training of technical field personnel. In this regard, they underscored the need to strengthen the capacities of local actors. To understand the impact, they emphasized that it is key to address local aspirations and needs, for example in processes such as the designation of protected areas, and to have clarity about community expectations where they work.

Another important point that was mentioned is that although a lot of information is generated in the country, it comes mainly from non-governmental organizations and not from universities, which shows the need to build bridges between both sectors. Advances in new forms of dissemination were also mentioned, as well as the urgency of innovating in intellectual property issues, prior and informed consent, and the ratification of the Escazú Agreement, which implies an internal reflection on what intellectual property means in these contexts.

Finally, it was highlighted that in order to strengthen the three I's, it is essential to build connections between researchers who work within the same territories, but where work goals and activity overlaps and complementarities have not been articulated. Bolivian participants found that the workshop served precisely as a space for articulation, which opened opportunities for collaboration and generated new ideas to work together in the future.

Colombia:

The Colombian group emphasized the need to involve different actors throughout all stages of the research. They pointed out that from the beginning it is essential to have clear conversations about data treatment and ownership. From the beginning, agreements must be established with the different parties involved in and/or affected by the research processes. They also highlighted the importance of integrating social data with data from the natural sciences, which implies developing methodologies that allow both types of information to be articulated.

They also reflected on how to ground the three I's in everyday practice, highlighting that inclusion is usually the most difficult to implement. In relation to the dissemination of results, the group agreed that it is necessary to go beyond the production of academic articles and explore other avenues, creating products in the languages of local communities, without technicalities and in more understandable formats. They recognized, however, the difficulty of reconciling multiple expectations, especially in a context marked by institutional schedules and complex bureaucracies, which often limit the real possibilities of integrating different actors in innovation processes.

In addition, the importance of transparency, constant reflection, and self-criticism was discussed. So that expectations are not generated when projects have limited budgets and time, they emphasized recognizing how far it is possible to go in terms of meaningful participation. This must be accompanied by open communication, where clear boundaries can be established based on the ethical principles discussed in the previous day's session.

From a social science perspective, it was underlined that much of the research is still dominated by natural and biological approaches, focused on statistical data and measurements. Based on community work experiences, the value of integrating biological data with social data from the

Another key issue was the need to question the position from which one arrives in the territory, recognizing that many times one enters with a sense of moral superiority. External actors must be willing to embrace that learning is non-linear and extends in both directions. Finally, the value of interdisciplinarity was underlined and an additional dimension was added - to ensure that research has a political impact and that findings extend beyond just the academic arena.

Guyana:

This group highlighted the interest in strengthening research methodologies. This included work in the forest canopy, as well as the development of new technical capabilities such as environmental DNA and other artificial intelligence tools. These should be accompanied by the creation of local laboratories that allow data to be analyzed in the territories rather than follow traditional extractive research logics.

They also identified communication as a key area to strengthen within teams so that information flows appropriately to generate more horizontal relationships.

The importance of scaling the results and connecting different points of the Amazon was also discussed, to build a more regional understanding that complements local studies and allows us to see the diversity of conditions in the territory.

Finally, it was stressed that it is not enough to disseminate results, but it is key to share them in more intimate spaces and directly. This allows for the opening of spaces for other actors to interpret and react to findings, especially those who were involved in some way in the process of generating questions and collecting data.

Brazil:

A key lesson of this group was the need to pay greater attention to urban nature. It was mentioned, for example, that in Amazonian cities such as Tefé, there is a high biological diversity in urban environments that has not yet been sufficiently studied. Collaborative science can be a key avenue to address this gap.

The value of developing a diverse research group, with gender balance and Indigenous and non-Indigenous participation, was also highlighted. This enabled very rich discussions around the three "I's": innovation, impact, and inclusion. Indigenous voices from this Brazilian group pointed out that, while the very deep experience of territorial care is beginning to be increasingly recognized in different spheres, discussions continue to be guided by Western frameworks of thought. In other words, while acknowledging the importance of the discussions and reflections that have taken place during these days of the workshop, they are considered to follow a matrix of positivist thought that, for example, separates humans from nature, earth from heaven. From Indigenous worldviews, this fragmentation does not exist. The human is part of nature. This tension was evident, in particular, in the exercises of the three "I's" and the reflection on ethical dilemmas. Here, stages of the research responded to logics dictated by the scientific method. The way in which results were presented, for example, through posters, was also mentioned as another expression of Western academic formats that do not always dialogue with other ways of producing and sharing knowledge.

From this, they stressed that there is a need to rethink the tools of innovation, impact, and inclusion from Indigenous thought matrices, recognizing that there is not a single way to conceive these categories. The importance of opening debates between worldviews was raised as a necessary step to situate the three "I's" in specific contexts. In this sense, science and research can function as spaces for intercultural dialogue.

Finally, the centrality of Indigenous peoples in Brazil was highlighted, particularly in the Amazon, where they represent a significant proportion of the territory. Indigenous peoples do not need to become conservationists or ecologists, as many of their practices have historically been organic forms of conservation. It is from this cosmology that innovation, impact, and inclusion must be contemplated.

Figure 20. Participant sharing in plenary his reflection on the lessons learned

2. Shared learning: what we bring and what we take away

Facilitators posed two questions to workshop participants: First, *what innovative practice do you take away from the workshop?* And then, *what innovative practice did you bring to the workshop?* Each participant responded in a quick round, sharing their ideas concisely. Table 7 summarizes these responses, organizing them by thematic categories to facilitate visualization of common patterns and to highlight the diversity of approaches to innovation, inclusion, impact, technology, ethics, and governance in research and collaboration processes.

Table 7. Answers to the question: What innovative practice did you take home? and What practice did you bring?

Category	Innovative practice you take home	Innovative practice you brought
Technology/Methods	Use of Artificial Intelligence to think of ideas in the formulation of projects, camera traps, environmental DNA, tools for rapid information gathering	Using dogs for monitoring, environmental DNA, technological tools for citizen participation
Inclusion/Participation	Integrate indigenous and traditional science, co-creation with communities, inclusion of affective matters, constant dialogue	Projects co-designed with communities, training of Indigenous and university youth, citizen science
Knowledge integration	Integrating social and biological data, interdisciplinarity	Connection between spokespersons, integration of worldviews, integration of city and nature
Ethics/Governance	Apply the three "I's" plus ethics in each project to humanize science	Data ethics toolbox, data ownership defined from the start, community governance protocols
Outreach/Communication	Podcasts and youth, use of art, sharing indigenous knowledge	Illustrated guides in local languages, art and pedagogy in science, inclusive communication
Conceptual innovation	Paradigm shift, defragmenting science	Design thinking, reflective scaling-up, contextualized approaches to innovation

During the refreshment break, attendees were invited to connect with those participants with whom they would like to share more information about their projects and research, or those with whom they would like to forge future collaborations.

3. Final reflections

At the end of the workshop, the thematic leaders shared their impressions on the insights, complexities, and challenges of working in the Amazon region. The depth and intensity of the three days were highlighted, where each participant contributed unique knowledge, experiences, and perspectives. Reflecting on what has been learned is difficult, comparable to the complexity of the Amazon itself, where biodiversity, communities, and scientific knowledge interact.

The importance of integrating the three I's: innovation, inclusion and impact, was highlighted, along with the ethics. Ethics is not reduced to documents or protocols, but it is an attitude present throughout the entire process: from the formulation of projects to collection, analysis, and dissemination of data. Ethics also extends to the recognition of data ownership, confidentiality,

and equity in participation of local actors, and in the relationship with Indigenous and peasant communities.

This workshop experience showed that conservation cannot be conceived only as the protection of species or ecosystems, but must include an understanding of the problems, aspirations, and worldviews of the people who inhabit the region. The value of human connections and knowledge as a driver to strengthen collaboration, innovation, and research with impact was underlined. These connections include both interdisciplinary work and the integration of biological, social, cultural, and technological knowledge. Openness to diverse worldviews, particularly Indigenous ones, is crucial to rethinking innovation and inclusion from perspectives other than solely Western science, considering that humans and nature are intrinsically connected.

Figure 21. Reflection of the thematic leaders

The need for a paradigm shift was emphasized. Listening to and learning from communities, Indigenous peoples, and local practices is critical, avoiding a posture of superiority that is sometimes assumed by external conservationists. Co-creation, trust, and constant dialogue are essential tools, and it was highlighted that innovation can also arise from artistic, emotional, and technological approaches. It was mentioned that conservation can include urban spaces, where nature exists and can be studied and protected.

They also highlighted the importance of interdisciplinarity, experimentation with new methodologies and technologies (such as eDNA, camera traps, or artificial intelligence) and the integration of participatory processes that actively involve the local community. It was recognized that projects require flexibility and adaptation to local contexts, considering resource constraints, bureaucracy, and the varying levels of training of the actors involved.

Finally, the richness of working with a diversity of languages, cultures, academic backgrounds, and experiences was valued, allowing for the construction of collaboration networks and regional solidarity. The reflection concluded that conservation is not only a technical act, but a complex ethical and social exercise. That it requires listening, learning, co-creating, and maintaining openness to new forms of knowledge and interaction with the environment.

4. Workshop products and collective next steps

The organizing team explained that, from the detailed record of the workshops, several products are being generated that will be shared with the participants in the coming months. Each workshop held throughout the project will have: a detailed report of the activities and discussions that took place throughout the 3.5 days, an executive analysis, meeting videos, a WhatsApp group to maintain communications, and a summary graphic of the workshop. In addition, it is planned to share photos of participants and the posters made during the activities.

It was highlighted that the elaboration of these products takes time since it seeks to balance speediness with quality and rigor. The participation and knowledge provided by all attendees was appreciated and they will be recognized as contributors in the detailed report. The importance of these documents not being "dead" was underlined, but rather, that they serve for future reference, support for developing ideas, and continuity of projects. To strengthen legitimacy and facilitate their scholarly use, the reports and executive summary will be given a DOI number, allowing them to be cited in future research. Finally, it was stated that the proximate session on next steps will discuss more concretely how this information will be used and shared.

Figure 22. Workshop participants during plenary discussion

The main objective of the next steps session was to generate a space in which attendees could direct the future of the group and networks consolidated during the workshop. To circumvent unrealistic expectations of long-term actions, organizers emphasized that while there would be logistical support and follow-up, the decision on what to do and how to maintain the network was mostly in the hands of the participants.

A brainstorming dynamic was opened in pairs and then plenary, in which the participants shared proposals on how to give continuity to collective work emerging from this workshop. Among the ideas were the development of scientific articles documenting experiences of community participation and research methodologies, the use of podcasts to disseminate innovative conservation experiences, the creation of a book club of articles on the Amazon, and the exchange of participatory methodologies to build trust among diverse actors. The possibility of forming smaller, thematic working groups was discussed, which could focus on specific aspects such as Indigenous knowledge, participatory science, or the use of technologies.

From these discussions, concrete next steps were defined. To begin with, it was proposed to organize a series of five webinars over the next year on different topics:

- a) Artificial intelligence applied to conservation research
- b) Participatory research and knowledge dialogues
- c) Use of camera traps in the forest canopy
- d) Science for decision-making in protected areas
- e) Data ethics and participatory science tools.

Each webinar will have a person in charge and can be opened to a wider audience. Assuming a virtual context, the meetings could count on multi-language interpretation and event recording. In addition, it was proposed to keep the WhatsApp group active to share information, calls and funding opportunities, and the possibility of organizing additional workshops or virtual meetings according to participant interests and availability. The central idea was to consolidate the initial networking and collaborative relationships, ensuring that workshop products, reports, executive summaries, and posters could be presented and used by participants in their respective contexts, including interactions with local authorities or decision-makers in each country.

Figure 23. Workshop participants during plenary activity

About the project “Power of Connections”

The "Power of Connections" project is led by the Tropical Conservation and Development Program (TCD) of the Center for Latin American Studies at the University of Florida (UF), in partnership with the Gordon and Betty Moore Foundation. "Learning lessons and strengthening coalitions for the conservation of the Amazon" is at the heart of this project, which seeks to connect people and collaboratively develop pathways for the lasting conservation of the Pan-Amazon. This project is funded by the Gordon and Betty Moore Foundation through GBMF13270 grants.

About TCD

The mission of the Tropical Conservation and Development Program (TCD) is to connect theory and practice to promote biodiversity conservation, sustainable use of natural resources, and human well-being in the tropics and beyond. TCD is a research and training program of the University of Florida's Center for Latin American Studies, with 10 tenured faculty and approximately 100 affiliated faculty across campus. The program has a long history of collaboration with partner organizations in the Amazon and support networks of conservation professionals committed to sustainable development.

About the Moore Foundation

The Gordon and Betty Moore Foundation promotes scientific discovery, environmental conservation, and the special character of the San Francisco Bay Area. Since 2001, its Andes-Amazon Initiative has helped conserve more than 400 million hectares in the Amazon. By 2031, the initiative aims to ensure that 70% of the Amazon biome (forest cover) and the freshwater ecosystems that support it are under effective management and conservation. Visit Moore.org and follow [@MooreFound](https://twitter.com/MooreFound) for more information.

APPENDIX

A. Complete and detailed workshop agenda

Objectives:

1. Create a community among participants
2. Advance the thinking on innovation in the research process in the Amazon
3. Exchange experiences: Methods/tools, Lessons learned and successes
4. Discuss best ethical practices
5. Discuss and plan next steps

Day 0 - Introduction Session

Time	Activity	Detail
7:00 pm	Welcoming words by Corine Vriesendorp, Director of Science at Conservación Amazónica - ACCA	Corine Vriesendorp, welcomed participants and introduced the ACCA team supporting the event.
7:15 pm	Welcoming words by Karen Kainer, Faculty, UF / TCD - POC	Karen Kainer, UF - TDC- Power of Connection, joined and welcomed participants to the workshop.
7:30pm	Introduction to Themed Leaders.	Karen Kainer introduced Themed Leaders: Myriam and Marisol.
	Introduction to the Facilitator Team.	Karen also introduced the facilitator team: Jon Dain (UF-TCD) and Pamela Montero (independent consultant).
7:45 pm	Introduction to the rest of the UF / TCD - POC team.	Karen Kainer introduced the rest of the team members to the participants, indicating their role and affiliation: Bette, Pilar, Vanessa Luna, Johanna Espin, Ana Garrido.
	Introducing the Three Topics participants will work on during the workshop.	Jon Dain presents to participants the three topics they will work on: <i>Bring an innovative idea or practice</i> <i>Leave with an innovative idea or practice</i> <i>Make a new and useful connection</i>
8:00 pm	Sharing a Summary of the Project POC (timeline).	Karen Kainer shared with participants the dynamic, key events and overall purpose of the project Power of Connections .

Time	Activity	Detail
8:15 pm	Presenting the Objectives of the Workshop.	We presented and clarified the objectives for the workshop: <i>Create community among participants</i> <i>Advance thinking on innovation in research process in the Amazon</i> <i>Discuss best ethical practices</i> <i>Discussion/Plan next steps</i>
8:30 pm	Presenting Symbolic Objects & Map	We asked participants to present the symbolic object they brought from their territory, place of origin, or institution. The objects were displayed in a visible location throughout the duration of the meeting. We also asked participants to place their place in the Amazon where they work, or they live, or they were born.
8:45 pm	Closing and final information for next days	Vanessa Luna closed the evening and provided information about the next day's meal dynamic. Participants were also asked to sign the photo and video release form.
9:00 pm	Dinner	

Day 1

Time	Activity	Detail
8:00 am	Welcome	During the welcoming we ensure participants feel connected and develop a sense of collective effort and collaboration. We asked participants in order to secure a full spectrum of interaction to change the place they sit. This way they could interact with different participants. We presented the “Eureka” flipchart where participants could share innovative ideas. As a group we discussed housekeeping rules to have a respectful interaction.

Time	Activity	Detail
9:00 am	Advance the Thinking: defining key terms and concepts: <i>Innovation, Impact and Inclusivity</i>	<p>During this stage participants were asked to answer the following <i>Key Questions</i>: “<i>In Amazon conservation research, what does innovation mean to you?</i>”</p> <p>The purpose of this activity was to conceptualize innovation among participants. After the individual conceptualization, participants formed small groups and then shared in plenary.</p> <p>This process streamlined contributions and built from individual perspective towards a collective understanding of complex concepts such as <i>innovation, impact and inclusion</i>.</p>
10.30 am	Break	
10.50 am	Continue: Advance the Thinking.	<p>They were asked the following questions: “<i>In your experience, what makes research in the Amazon impactful?</i>”, and “<i>In your experience, what makes research on Amazon inclusive?</i>”</p> <p>Each question, they reflected in groups and then shared them in plenary.</p>
11:50 am	Reflections by Themed Leaders	Marisol and Myrian shared in plenary their reflections based on the participants' work and collective effort.
1:00 pm	Lunch	
2:45 pm	Introducing team of professional Translators	The team of professional translators were also introduced to the participants. The translators showed the dynamic and use of equipment.
3:00 pm	Exchange experiences: Poster Preparation	<p>Participants were asked to create and share posters to showcase innovative, impactful, and inclusive initiatives.</p> <p>Participants were given time, and resources to expand their creativity.</p>
4:30 pm	Break	

Time	Activity	Detail
4:50 pm	Exchange experiences: Mercado / Market Activity	<p>During this activity participants placed their poster on the walls, then rotated by groups to present their poster.</p> <p>During the presentation, they could answer questions, present their findings and create connections. Additionally, they reflected on how their research was innovative, impactful and inclusive. This was highlighted in the posters.</p> <p>Participants were asked to place their names on posters they would like to further a connection.</p>
6:00 pm	Closing the day	<p>We made a daily wrap-up, highlighting what participants worked today. Additionally, stated the objectives of the workshop and how we've been addressing them.</p> <p>Vanessa Luna closed the day providing information about dinner, and logistic issues.</p>

Day 2

Time	Activity	Detail
8:00 am	Welcome	<p>During the welcoming we ensured participants felt connected and developed a sense of collective effort and collaboration.</p> <p>We shared a summary of the previous day and reviewed the agenda of the day.</p>
9:00 am	Continue Exchange experiences: Market	Participants continue presenting their posters and creating a community.
10.30 am	Break	
10.50 am	Discussion about Ethical considerations you faced and how you solved them (2).	We asked participants to locate in the pre-made flipcharts displaying previously identified research steps ethical considerations and how they solved them using a case study approach. Participants formed groups, and then they shared those experiences in plenary.

Time	Activity	Detail
1:00 pm	Lunch	
2:45 pm	Continue Discussion about Ethical considerations (2).	(cont.)
4:30 pm	Break	
4:50 pm	Continue Discussion about Ethical considerations (3).	(cont.)
6:00 pm	Closing the day	Facilitators closed the day and provided general guidelines for the next day (times), and meal hours.

Day 3

Time	Activity	Detail
8:00 am	Welcome	During the welcoming we ensured participants felt connected and developed a sense of collective effort and collaboration. We shared a summary of the previous day and reviewed the Agenda of the day.
9:00	Lessons Learned.	Participants reflected on their research or initiatives using the three key topics discussed: innovation, impact, and inclusion. They responded to the guiding question: <i>What insights or knowledge will make your work more innovative, impactful, and inclusive?</i> Their reflections were informed by the first day’s work on the conceptual approach, posters, and ethical considerations. The activity began with individual reflection, followed by small-group discussions by country, and concluded with sharing in plenary.
10.30 am	Break	
10.50 am	Working on the Power of Connections	We asked participants to talk to someone they would like to further the connection based on their Poster presentation. This was an unstructured space for participants to connect and discuss topics of interest leading to the creation of powerful connections.

Time	Activity	Detail
11:20 am	Working on the ideas they take, and they bring to the Workshop	<p>We asked participants to write in individual cards the following questions: <i>What idea are you taking from the workshop?</i> <i>What idea did you bring to the workshop?</i></p> <p>We asked them to write in individual cards, and then place them in the corresponding flipchart: <i>“Ideas you are taking from the workshop”</i> and <i>“Ideas you brought to the workshop”</i>. The cards were presented in plenary.</p>
12:20 pm	Reflection and highlights by themed leaders.	Myrian and Marisol shared their insights from the workshops, posters and other reflection activities.
1:00 pm	Lunch	
2:45 pm	Next Steps	Karen Kainer and Vanessa Luna shared with participants the next steps for the project Power of Connections, including expected products and events.
3:15 pm	Enabling spaces for the Power of Connections to develop	We enabled space for participants to lead initiatives or actions related to the project POC. We asked them: <i>“What do you want to do with this group?”</i>
4:30 pm	Break	
4:50	Gallery Walk	
5:10 pm	Evaluation of the Workshop	Vanessa Luna shared with participants an online survey.
5:30 pm	Conclusions	
6:00 pm	Closing the day	